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Editorial - Welcoming the first European peer review scientific journal created for and curated by school students

Giannakopoulou Alik
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Welcoming the first European peer-review scientific journal created for and curated by school students

Giannakopoulou Alik, Ellinogermaniki Agogi

giannakopoulou@ea.gr

Introduction: Aims of the journal

We are extremely honored to present you the first issue of the newly established journal (Open Schools for Open Societies Journal). This service accepts original papers written by school age students from Primary to Secondary schools across Europe under the mentoring of their teachers on all aspects of Science, Engineering and Technology. The Journal is available through the platform of the National Documentation Centre in Greece (EKT) and coordinated by Ellinogermaniki Agogi with a new issue coming up every three months. It accepts articles currently in English (in special issues articles in other languages are also accepted).

The main aim of the journal is to introduce students to the work of publishing scientific data, open science and open data aspects. The journal follows the same principles as any scientific journal simulating a valuable process for students where they must build their articles following the journal template, back their findings, collaborate with their peers and teachers, use references, follow deadlines, accept critique and eventually share openly their work with the rest of the scientific and student community. Journal reviewers are researchers as well as educators to ensure that the published content is of high quality. This initiative not only empowers young people to share their work outside their classroom walls, but it additionally introduces them to an essential part of the work of a researchers that hardly ever is touched upon the regular educational system.

The Editorial Board of the Journal consists of representatives of universities, science centres and museums, schools and research centres coming from the OpenAIRE Project as well as the OSOS (Open Schools for Open Societies) project based in 10 countries in Europe and Israel.

Journal Content

We accept articles under any theme across the field of STEM, thus Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics. The work published must be original work conducted by the students themselves either in or outside their classroom. Authors are invited to write in a language that can be understood by other peer students avoiding jargon.

Acknowledgments

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